

Intralaminar and interlaminar progressive failure analysis of AFP composite on a tow level

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Introduction

Process-induced defects in AFP manufacturing:

Limitations of previous AFP composites modelling approaches

- Tows are *uniform* and *continuous* (neglect the impact of defects & tow interactions)
- All the plies have to be *consistent* (impractical assumption if defects are introduced)
- Relatively *simple* geometries (zero curvature geometries: Flat plate or cylindrical shell)

*Tatting, B. F., Gürdal, Z., *Design and manufacture of elastically tailored tow placed plates*. Tech. Rep., NASA, Langley Research Center, Hampton, VA, NASA/CR-2002-211919; August 2002.

Objective

- To develop a more detailed numerical model that can efficiently model AFP composites with induced defects
- To demonstrate the capabilities of modelling overlapping tows with unaligned mesh
- The capability of modelling intralaminar failure and interlaminar failure

Method

Stacked Shell Approach

Cohesive Zone Model

- The cohesive contact will be used instead of the cohesive element due to meshing difficulties of the interface and unaligned mesh between adjacent tows.
- The capabilities of modelling failures of the stacked shell cohesive contact (SSCC) model will be demonstrated through several benchmark tests against the published simulation/experimental data.

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB)

Aligned mesh

Unaligned mesh

Loading conditions of DCB

Simulation result & validation

Laminate Coupon – Interaction between Failure Modes

FE model of laminate coupon

Simulation result & validation

Final delamination diagram*

Delamination plot of each interface

*Hallett SR, Jiang W-G, Khan B, Wisnom MR. Modelling the interaction between matrix cracks and delamination damage in scaled quasi-isotropic specimens. *Composites Science and Technology*. 2008;68(1):80-9.

Conclusion & Future Work

- The accuracy and feasibility of SSCC model in modelling delamination progression has been demonstrated.
- The simulation results also shows the SSCC model is not sensitive to the mesh distortion and mesh size.
- Modelling the intralaminar and interlaminar failure of physical AFP composites on a tow level will be carried out and validated against experimental results.

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